

A Model of Transformational Leadership of Private Schools in Khon Kaen, Thailand

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Article Info	Abstract
Article History	<p><i>This research's objectives were: 1) to study the current and desirable conditions and transformational leadership of private schools in KhonKaen Province; 2) to develop a transformational leadership model of private schools in KhonKaen Province. The study is divided into 5 phases as follows. Phase 1: Composition studies: it was conducted by synthesizing ideas, principles, theories, and related research work to obtain the components to be determined as a conceptual framework. Phase 02: the study of the current and desirable conditions was carried out by collecting quantitative data from the population, including 128 private school administrators and 2,482 private school teachers (in total 2,610) and 360 randomly selected samples including 128 private school administrators and 232 private school teachers. The questionnaire used to collect the data had its mean content validity of 0.84 and confidence coefficient of 0.96. The obtained data were analysed by using software packages to find the following statistics: Frequency, Percentage, Mean and Standard Deviation. Phase 3: the development of a transformational leadership model; this was performed by taking the mean of the current condition data and desirable condition data to find the need value or PNI modified. Phase 4: collecting the qualitative data; this was conducted by organizing a Focus Group Discussion of 10 experts. Phase 5: collecting the qualitative data, it was conducted by organizing the public hearing from five highly-performing private schools consisting of one school administrator, five teachers each (a total of 35 people). The results of the analysis showed that the transformational leadership model of private schools in KhonKaen Province was statistically rated at a moderate level. The needs were sorted: 1) ideological influence, 2) inspiration, 3) cognitive stimulation, and 4) individual consideration.</i></p>
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Introduction

Today the world is changing rapidly in social, economic, political, and technological aspects resulted from the development of information technology. Population quality is a crucial factor in driving the policy towards success and international competitiveness (Office of the Education Council Secretariat, 2007). The world society in the new century tends to change and become more competitive. As Thailand is part of the world society, it is inevitable to be affected by the change in both the public and private sectors that must adjust to a new management model in order to be able to cope with such situations by introducing new management techniques or tools or strengthening the performance of the work. In particular, it is necessary to develop transformational leadership (Sirirak Nukdontree, 2017).

Modern school administrators face a variety of problems under constantly changing situations. The organization has been adjusted according to the changing policy to improve the quality of the organization as a whole system in response to the situation (Paradee Anantwaree, 2014). Transformational leadership is a feature of school administrators, motivating to see the vision and goals of the school and encouraging challenges and enthusiasm about working, focusing on the achievement of work, playing a role in creating teamwork, pushing for change at the educational institution level by encouraging mutual learning. It is also a model for learning as a counsellor, giving advice to teachers. Therefore, the school administrators should have a transformational leadership in the school administration to build a quality school to be recognized, leading to success in educational management and to improving learners' learning according to the goals of education and national development (Pornwadee Prasertdee, 2015).

Private educational institutions must be managed with caution for self-development, sustainable quality, acceptance of students, parents, society, communities, and a growing number of students every year. School administrators need transformational leadership, have an excellent immune vision. Even if there is an internal

and external change effect, the schools can reach the desired destination and success (Akkarach Kositpimanvach, 2017). Of such importance, researchers are interested in studying the transformational leadership development model of private schools in KhonKaen Province as a guideline in setting up the school's operational policy and as a systematic change leadership development model to solve problems effectively and to develop the potential of learners.

Objectives

This research's objectives were: 1) to study the current and desirable conditions and transformational leadership of private schools in KhonKaen Province; 2) to develop a transformational leadership model of private schools in KhonKaen Province.

Research Methodology

Phase 1: Composition studies: it was conducted by synthesizing ideas, principles, theories, and related research work to obtain the components to be determined as a conceptual framework.

Phase 02: the study of the current and desirable conditions was carried out by collecting quantitative data from the population, including 128 private school administrators and 2,482 private school teachers (in total 2,610) and 360 randomly selected samples including 128 private school administrators and 232 private school teachers. The questionnaire used to collect the data had its mean content validity of 0.84 and confidence coefficient of 0.96. The obtained data were analysed by using software packages to find the following statistics: Frequency, Percentage, Mean, Standard Deviation.

Phase 3: the development of a transformational leadership model; this was performed by taking the mean of the current condition data and desirable condition data to find the necessary value or PNI_{modified} .

Phase 4: collecting the qualitative data; this was conducted by organizing a Focus Group Discussion of 10 experts.

Phase 5: collecting the qualitative data; it was conducted by organizing the public hearing from five highly-performing private schools consisting of one school administrator, five teachers each (a total of 35 people).

Data Analysis

VPhase 1: synthesizes elements from the concepts, principles, theories, and related research work of educators and scholars to frame the research concept.

Phase 2: using a program to analyze statistical data as follows:

- 1) Status of the respondents using frequency and percentage;
- 2) current and desirable condition levels using the mean and standard deviation.

Phase 3: Needs using PNI_{modified} to sort.

$$PNI_{\text{modified}} = I - D$$

I = Mean of Desirable Conditions

D = Mean of Current Conditions

Phase 4: data analysis obtained from Focus Group Discussions included content analysis according to the conceptual framework and other issues.

Phase 5: data were analyzed for frequency (f) and percentage (higher than 50% of the Evaluation Form) to verify private schools' transformational leadership in KhonKaen Province. This consists of the suitability, usefulness, and possibility aspects.

Table 1. Transformational leadership of private schools in KhonKaen Province

Transformational leadership	Current Conditions			Desirable Conditions			PNI_{modified}	Orders of PNI_{modified}
	\bar{X}	S.D.	Level	\bar{X}	S.D.	Level		
1. Inspiration	2.74	.68	moderate	4.53	.50	highest	.65	2
2. Intellectual stimulation	2.73	.87	moderate	4.47	.50	high	.64	3
3. Ideological influence	2.61	.92	moderate	4.47	.50	high	.71	1
4. Individual consideration	2.91	.63	moderate	4.52	.50	highest	.55	4
5. Information technology advancement	3.71	.80	high	4.45	.49	high	.20	5
Sum	2.94	.36	moderate				.53	

Table 1 indicates that the current condition of transformational leadership of private schools in KhonKaen Province was statistically rated at a moderate level (\bar{X} = 2.94, S.D = .36). The studied aspect with the highest level of opinion was 'information technology advancement' (\bar{X} = 3.71, S.D = .80), followed by 'individual

consideration' (\bar{X} = 2.91, S.D = .63) and the lowest level of opinion was 'Ideological influence' (\bar{X} = 2.61, S.D = .92), respectively.

The desirable conditions of transformational leadership of private schools in KhonKaen Province in overall average was rated at a high level (\bar{X} = 4.49, S.D = .37). The aspect with the highest level of opinion is 'inspiration' (\bar{X} = 4.53, S.D = .50) was followed by 'individual consideration' (\bar{X} = 4.52, S.D = .50) and the lowest level of opinion was 'Information technology advancement' (\bar{X} = 4.45, S.D = .49)', respectively.

Sorting of the importance of needs is essential. The need that was more important than the mean of the PNI_{modified} index, herein (0.53), it was found that 'Ideological influence' (PNI_{modified} = 0.71) must be development first, followed by 'Inspiration' (PNI_{modified}= 0.65), 'Intellectual stimulation' (PNI_{modified} = 0.64), 'Individual consideration' (PNI_{modified} = 0.55). For 'information technology advancement', its value (PNI_{modified}= 0.20) was less than the mean PNI_{modified} value, thus eliminated. The researchers put the results in order of importance again as follows: 1) ideological influence, 2) inspiration, 3) intellectual stimulation, 4) individual consideration.

Results

The transformational leadership models of private schools in KhonKaen Province are as follows:

Ideological influence

1) Set the direction of the school with a focus on developing learners' learning as a priority; 2) communicate to create understanding to teachers, staff, the community, and other stakeholders about the school's vision and operations clearly; 3) create a feeling of being part of the team by setting vision, goals, and working together; 4) allow all parties to participate in setting goals, vision, and mission of the school; 5) always behave as an example of a learner by receiving training and development, exchange of knowledge and new methods of school administration to improve learners' learning.

Inspiration

1) Establish policies, working systems, and teamwork culture; 2) establish policies and guidelines for teachers to join together to learn and exchange professional experiences to develop learners' learning; 3) support activities that promote the creation of a culture for fostering respect and mutual trust and good interactions within the school; 4) provide opportunities for teachers to present learners' success stories as a result of development efforts and teachers' learning management; 5) set criteria for assessing teacher performance based on the operational success as a team, give morale to teachers who are committed to learning and professional self-development, and contribution to the development of learning for learners.

Intellectual stimulation

1) Organize training to increase the knowledge of teachers about the guideline for learner development in relation to the problem of the learners and the needs of teachers; 2) set a schedule for teachers to meet, exchange knowledge and learn experiences of work, observe, explore class, plan and develop together to find ways to improve learning management; 3) always ask questions for teachers to ponder the problem, assumptions and solutions or the development of learners; 4) support the budget for professional development training and learning management for teachers; 5) build educational networks with other organizations for the benefit of cooperation in professional development of teachers.

Individual Consideration

1) Give advice, guidance, and mentor to each teacher about personal development to have professional expertise, leading to the development of the quality of learning in an admirable manner of investigation to motivate and motivate teachers; 2) supervise, monitor, evaluate the performance or assign a constant evaluation of the performance of each teacher on a regular basis, reflect the performance of the work focusing on promoting development professional practice and developing learners' learning; 3) give each teacher an opportunity to present, exchange visions, values, reflect weaknesses and strengths in learning; 4) encourage teachers to choose training sessions to develop oneself according to their needs; 5) provide opportunities for each teacher to make decisions on learning management or to solve problems of the students in accordance with the state of the problem and the needs of each student.

Discussion

According to the research, it was found that the current status of the transformational leadership of private schools in KhonKaen Province in overall was at a moderate level. It showed that the transformational leadership is not high enough. This is consistent with Kopkit Thammanuchit (2015) who commented that school administrators need more development of knowledge and experience. The private school administrators should have transformational leadership in line with the changes in the world society in the globalized age to keep pace

with the development of the world in the future. There are studies that show that transformational leadership as measured by tools and measures of multicomponent influence the performance of individuals and organizations (Bass & Avolio, 1994). Therefore, the transformational leadership concept is a synergistic significance to the school administration (Sirirak Nukdontree, 2017). Thai education has a problem in terms of implementation which is the process of implementing the curriculum to design the learning management or to achieve the learning standard of the basic education curriculum. Therefore, the school administrators need to find a way to manage and resolve the said problem. Here, the concept of '8 Forces of Change' is used as a guideline for building transformational leadership in the school (Fullan, 2008). Managing a successful organization requires change management and constant development. The elements of change management are as follows: participating in and accepting from people within the environmental framework; understand and know where the organization stands logically; know the goal and success indicators, methods achieve goals or objectives; leaders' plan to allow people in the organization to express their opinions (Kotter, 2012).

The importance of needs is the first priority that should be developed. In terms of ideological influence, in line with the previous scholarly work of Pongpetch thongin (2011) 'A Study of Conditions and Approaches to Transformational Leadership Development of Public-School Administrators in Chiang Rai Province' which commented that administrators should set the direction of the school with a focus on developing learners' learning. It is important to communicate and create an understanding of stakeholders. The direction of action is clear to create a feeling of belonging to a team. All parties are given opportunities to set goals, vision and mission of the school. The administrators behave as an example for self-development in terms of learning new ways of school administration focusing on the development of learners' learning. This is in line with the concept of Kotter (2012), where eight steps were proposed for successful management of change, mentioned in the book 'Leading Change' which deals with influencing ideology, motivating people establish the greater sense of urgency, creating the guiding coalition by bringing the right people with passion for work and skills into the assigned work, have the right vision (development & vision and strategy), bring the team together to define the vision and work strategy to create commitment, understanding of the change vision. Also, the communication should be useful, easy to understand and meet people's needs.

The second priority of need is inspiration in line with the research of Jaruwan Wongday (2009), 'Approaches to developing transformational leadership among school administrators that affect teacher performance satisfaction under the Office of the Tak Educational Service Area 1' commenting that management should set up a policy and team culture by aiming to help develop learners' learning, organize good relations activities within the school to foster effective collaboration, give teachers an opportunity to exchange problem-solving methods, consider merit aimed at encouraging teachers' commitment to developing learning for learners. This is also consistent with the concept of Fullan (2007) in creating commitment and understanding (or engaging people's moral purpose) to provide knowledge and understanding of the members of the organization on the reasons why change has to be made. To build capacity of members of the organization, they have knowledge and understanding of policies, strategies, resources, and operational methods that lead to mutual cooperation. In driving the system of change, both at the school level and country-level (Fullan, 2007) outlined five key elements that are essential to driving educational change: developing new knowledge and skills, building a learning society, clarifying change, accessing to resources and development of leadership at the institutional level. In addition, understanding the process of change which is a difficult process, it is necessary to have a leader with the ability to deal with challenges. Therefore, it must be invested in energy, ideas, and determination that contribute to the development of such a change. The development of a culture for learning is the creation of a learning society, which is a key factor in the success of the transformation. This is a channel for members of the organization to exchange and learn from each other to create a commitment to combining cooperation towards development.

The third priority of need is intellectual stimulation, in line with Pornwadee Prasertdee (2015) 'The study of the condition and the transformational leadership development of the school administrators under the Sukhothai Educational Service Area Office 2' suggesting that the educational institution should organize training to increase teaching potential for teachers and to develop learners, organize the meeting to exchange knowledge, experiences and planning. This is in accordance with Kotter (2012) who has expressed the idea of empowering other to act by eliminating obstacles. It must be rewarding and supported by leaders, recognize progress and what has been achieved, create short-term wins, set goals that can be straightforwardly achieved. The new management must be initiated and must be successful before starting to do something new. It must inspire and persevere to change or consolidate gains and produce even more change. This is encouraged to make progress reports and create a culture of change (institutionalizing changes in the culture); values of success must be emphasized by changes in the culture of the organization, taken into account the virtues of coexistence.

The fourth need is individual consideration in line with the research of Sirirak Nukdontree (2017), led to the development of transformational leadership in school administration to become a professional learning community under the Office of the Secondary Education Service Area 5. This study commented that executives must have leadership as a mentor providing advice to the persons involved, leading to the development of the

quality of learning and reflecting on performance with aims to promote the development of learners' learning. The administrators should provide an opportunity to exchange knowledge according to their own way and teachers can choose to develop their own training according to requirement. They are able to make decisions about learning management, able to solve problems according to the condition and needs of individual students. This is in line with the concept of Fullan (2007) that leadership for change: developing cultures of evaluation should be accompanied by a culture of learning. It is to find the meaning of what is gained by the exchange in the learning society. One of the key strategies for educational transformation is to measure and evaluate results for learning, to use information to create the action plan for development and for building a culture. The key to assessing learning outcomes is self-assessment of the school. The results of the assessment help to identify the strengths and weaknesses of the development, leading to the success of the education.

Recommendations

Recommendations for the use of research results

At the national level, from the research results, the opinions of the school administrators and teachers were at the moderate level, Ministry of Education should cultivate awareness among school administrators about transformational leadership and set it as a policy or a plan to develop executives to qualify for complete transformational leadership.

At the provincial level, where the regional supervision representative is KhonKaen Provincial Education Office, the research results can be used for supervision, follow up the driven action, set a development guideline of Private School Administrators in KhonKaen Province.

At the individual-level, for school administrators, these research results can be used to assess the transformational leadership status or to manage their own professional private schools. In other words, it is a guide to self-development and improve management.

Recommendations for the next research

There should be the study of transformational teachers' leadership in building learning communities in private schools leading to the development of learners' learning.

The study of transformational leadership in school administration, intellectual stimulation, and ideological influence should be made because the level of opinion is less practical.

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